

Land cover

- Open water
- Rice fields
- Uncultivated fields
- Mixed crop fields
- Cattail stands
- Floodplain and marshland
- Semi-arid grassland
- Bare
- Protected areas

Godwit core areas

- Dry season
- Wet season

